

European Swine Influenza Network Report #2 on Swine Influenza A Viruses Evolution and Diversity in Europe from October 2022 to September 2024

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Introduction

Swine Influenza A viruses (swIAVs) are prevalent among pigs in Europe and pose a significant threat to human health due to their potential spillover to humans and subsequent pandemic potential. The intensification of pig production systems and the unrestricted movement of live swine promote the spread of swIAV in Europe across national borders. Surveillance of swIAV evolution in Europe plays a crucial role in early detection of potential zoonotic or pandemic strains, facilitates informed decision-making in vaccine candidate selection and enhances overall public and veterinary health preparedness.

Recognizing the importance of coordinated efforts, the European Swine Influenza Network (ESFLU) has been established as a COST Action scientific network. Its primary objective is to foster scientific collaboration and enhance capacity at the European level for monitoring the evolution and spread of swIAVs, as well as identifying measures to prevent the spread of swIAVs within and between European countries. A pivotal component of ESFLU activities is the task undertaken by Working Group (WG) 2, which involves the annual compilation of a report detailing the evolution of swIAVs in Europe. This report is a result of collaborative efforts with ESFLU WG2 members sharing swIAV sequences derived from field samples collected and sequenced between October 2022 and October 2024. To achieve this, rigorous phylogenetic analyses were conducted on the compiled sequences and the results were made available online through a Nextstrain instance (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/esflu>). These analyses sought to determine the diversity of swIAVs in specific countries and their respective proportions based on the classification and analysis of all eight IAV segments. Moreover, the analyses aimed to ascertain whether specific viruses had potentially traversed national boundaries, indicating the cross-border movement of these viruses, or shared evolutionary history of viruses with the same genotype and closely related genes in several countries.

ESFLU WG2 also provides a crucial connection between ESFLU and OFFLU; the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) / Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) network of expertise on animal influenza. OFFLU performs bi-annual analyses of swIAVs circulating globally with the aim of identifying candidate vaccine viruses for pandemic preparedness (<https://www.offlu.org/index.php/offlu-vcv-summary-reports/>). As part of this activity, WG2 assists in the sharing of swIAV sequences between ESFLU members and OFFLU to facilitate increased resolution of swIAV diversity within ESFLU member countries. As such, this will help increase the output and visibility of ESFLU at the international level.

Regular updates of this nature are paramount for staying ahead of potential public and veterinary health threats. By continuously monitoring swIAV evolution in Europe, ESFLU WG2 reports endeavor to provide timely information to support enhanced preparedness of public health systems at the European level concerning swIAVs.

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Methods

The collected sequences were checked for their quality by removing sequences with more than 10 undetermined nucleotides (N) using `seqkit grep -s -r -v -p NNNNNNNNNN` (Shen et al., 2016). All segments were classified using the influenza sequences toolbox (https://github.com/gtrichard/influenza_sequences_toolbox) genotypeFasta tool using a modified version of the OctoFlu database available on the influenza sequences toolbox repository (Richard, 2025), with appropriate M pdm and NP pdm identification for swIAVs. Sequences were aligned separately using `mafft --auto` (Kato and Standley, 2013). Maximum-likelihood and time-scaled phylogenies were computed for all segments using the Nextstrain auspice pipeline (Hadfield et al., 2018) based on IQTREE2 (Minh et al., 2020) and TreeTime (Sagulenko et al., 2018).

Results

After two years of existence, the ESFLU Network collected sequences from 877 swIAV strains from 20 European countries across three separate calls for sequences concerning the following periods: October 2022 to September 2023 (228 swIAV strains), October 2023 to March 2024 (227 swIAV strains) and April 2024 to September 2024 (290 swIAV strains), as well as 132 strains sequences collected from GISAID. In total, over 6711 sequences were collected when combining all eight influenza A segments for each of the 877 strains, since most of the strains had full genome sequences (83.4%). The strains were genotyped using a modified OctoFlu database (Anderson et al., 2022) (see Methods). Their subtypes (HA and NA) diversity was categorized according to three levels of granularity: basic subtypes (e.g., H1N1, H1N2, H3N2), simple subtypes (Table 1, Figure 1, i.e. H1C/N1EA) and complete subtypes (Figure 2, i.e. H1C.2.1/N1EA). The samples were also genotyped based on the classification of all eight segments (Table 2).

At the simple subtype level (Table 1), the most widespread subtype in Europe is H1C/N1EA, which is found in 15 countries, followed by H1C/N2G found in 11 countries and H1A/N1P found in 10

countries. As expected from the literature, limited numbers of H3N2 strains were identified in Europe for the studied period (less than 12 per subtype). However, the 4th most widespread swIAV simple subtype in Europe was H3.2020/N2HS, found in six countries, which likely correspond to reverse zoonotic transmissions of human seasonal H3N2 viruses to swine, followed or not by circulation within the swine population. Despite few major clades present in most countries, each country displayed a specific combination of swIAV subtypes (Table 1) and a specific proportion of subtypes (Figure 1A). At the level of Europe, the frequencies of the different subtypes were relatively stable over the collection period (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: HA/NA simple subtypes of swIAV strains collected and sequenced in Europe between October 2022 and September 2024. **A.** Proportion of swIAV subtypes per country. The size of the pie charts is relative to the number of sequences. **B.** Frequency of swIAV simple subtypes over time in Europe. Interactive versions of the plots are available here: https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/HA?c=Subtype_simple.

Table 1: Presence / absence of swIAV subtypes in European countries monitored within the ESFLU network. The number of strains for each subtype at the level of Europe and the number of strains shared per country are indicated. HA H1A and NA N1P are from the pdm09 lineage. HA H1B and NA N2EU-4 and N2S (Scotland/94) are from the “human” lineage. HA H1C, NA N1EA are from the Eurasian avian-like lineage. HA H3 and NA N2G (Gent/84), NA N2HS are originating from H3N2 human seasonal lineages from various years. NA N2LAIV98 is originating from a H3N2 live attenuated vaccine (A/swine/Texas/4199-2/1998) and found in the USA up to recently (at least 2022).

Country ↓	Number of strains ↓	swIAV subtype →																						
		H1A/N1EA	H1A/N1P	H1A/N2G	H1B/N1EA	H1B/N2EU-4	H1B/N2G	H1B/N2LAIV98	H1C/N1EA	H1C/N1P	H1C/N2EU-4	H1C/N2G	H1C/N2LAIV98	H3/1970/N2G	H3/2000/N2G	H3/2010/N2S	H3/2010/N2EU-4	H3/2010/N2G	H3/2020/N2HS					
		52	67	47	1	5	32	1	15	310	2	13	302	1	4	5	1	2	2	2	2	2	11	
Austria	5																							
Belgium	45																							
Bulgaria	2																							
Czech Republic	4																							
Denmark	117																							
Finland	10																							
France	227																							
Germany	97																							
Greece	1																							
Italy	194																							
Netherlands	73																							
North Macedonia	2																							
Northern Ireland	2																							
Poland	16																							
Portugal	1																							
Russian Federation	21																							
Spain	3																							
Switzerland	30																							
Ukraine	2																							
United Kingdom	25																							
# of countries in which the subtype was found		4	10	3	1	1	5	1	2	15	2	1	11	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	6

At the complete subtypes level the classification of both HA and NA in different clades can be seen on Figure 2A. While the HA clades capture the diversity in a proper manner, some NA clades might remain at a reduced level of granularity such as the N1EA and N2G.2 clades which would require a subclassification (such as N1EA.1, N1EA.2, N2G.2.1, N2G.2.2...). However, despite the NA classification needing a more granular resolution, the 46 identified complete subtypes when taking into account the combined complete HA and NA clades render the visualisation at the scale of Europe quite complex (Figure 2B). Nevertheless, the combination of both HA and NA clades reveal highly different diversity profiles per country, with countries displaying a low number of swIAV complete subtypes like the United Kingdom (5), Belgium (8) or France (9), compared to countries displaying a high number of swIAV complete subtypes like Denmark (15), Italy (23) or Germany (13). The observed differences cannot only be explained by the sampling frequency alone as France had 227 strains for 9 complete subtypes compared to Italy with 197 strains for 23 complete subtypes and while the two countries have similar sampling strategies (passive surveillance). The most predominant HA clade in Europe for the considered period were H1A.3.3.2 and H1C.2.1 which were found in 11 countries. This was followed by H1C.2.2 and H1C.2.4, found in 10 countries each. For NA, N1EA was the most predominant in Europe (found in 15 countries), followed by N2G.2 (11 countries) and N1P (10 countries). For the HA/NA combinations, H1C.2.1/N1EA, H1C.2.2/N1EA and H1A.3.3.2/N1P were found in 10 countries each, followed by H1C.2.4.1/N2G.2 found in seven countries, H1A.3.3.2/N2G.2 found in six countries and H1C.2.2/N2G.2 found in five countries.

Figure 2: swIAV diversity at the complete subtypes level in Europe. **A.** Time-scaled HA/NA tanglegram. The phylogeny leaves are colored by HA clades and NA clades while the tanglegram lines are colored by the combined HA/NA subtypes. An interactive version of the plot is available here: https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/HA:groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/NA?c=Subtype_complete&p=full. **B.** Map of Europe with swIAV complete subtypes proportions by country. The size of the pie charts are scaled by the number of strains analysed in each country. An interactive version of the map is available here: https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/HA?c=Subtype_complete

Table 2: Genotypes table based on the OctoFlu influenza segments annotation. HA H1A.3.3.2, NA N1P and P internal genes are from the pdm09 lineage. HA H1C, NA N1EA and E internal genes are from the Eurasian avian-like lineage. HA H1B are from the “human” lineage. NA N2-EU-4 is found in H1B.1.2.2 strains from Italy (*A/swine/Italy/198260/2008*). NA N2 HS = human seasonal. H internal genes are from the human seasonal lineage. NA N2G = N2 Gent/84. NA N2S = Scotland/94. NA N2LAIV98 clade is originating from a H3N2 live attenuated vaccine (*A/swine/Texas/4199-2/1998*).

HA	NA	PB2	PB1	PA	NP	MP	NS	Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Czech Republic	Denmark	Finland	France	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	Northern Ireland	Poland	Russian Federation	Switzerland	United Kingdom
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	E	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	17	0	0	1	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	1	0	8	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N1P	P	P	P	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	1	4	0	16	0	12	2	1	3	11	0	3
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.1	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	E	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	10	0	2	0	2	4	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.1.1	N2S	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
H1B.1.1.2	N2S	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
H1B.1.1	N2LAIV98	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.2.1	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.2.1	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	7	0	0	0	2	5	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.2.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.2.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	P	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1B.1.2.2	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	1	0	0	1	9	76	1	21	3	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N1EA	P	P	E	P	P	E	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
H1C.2.1	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	13	0	0	0	0	5	5	15	13	0	0	0	21	0
H1C.2.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	2	0	0	28	2	17	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	E	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0
H1C.2.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.1	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	9	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	16	0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
H1C.2.4.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.2	N1P	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	3	0	106	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.2	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.3	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4	N2G.2	P	E	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.4	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.5	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.5	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H1C.2.5	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.1970.1	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.2000.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.2010.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
H3.2020.1	N2HS	H	H	H	H	H	H	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.Other-Human-2010	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.Other-Human-2010	N2EU4	P	P	P	P	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.Other-Human-2020	N2HS	H	H	H	H	H	H	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H3.Other-Human-2020	N2HS	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0

Concerning whole genomes, from the 877 strains received so far in the ESFLU project, whole genomes were available for 731 resulting in the same number of strains being genotyped (Table 2). In total, 70 different genotypes were identified. The genotypes were divided into four overall groups based on the lineage of the HA clade; H1A.3.3.2 of pdm09 origin, H1B.1 of human seasonal origin, H1C.2 of Eurasian avian-like H1N1 origin and H3 of both swine (swine-adapted Hong Kong H3N2/H3.1970.1/N2G.1) and human seasonal H3N2 origin. The genotypes were distributed in the four overall groups in 20 %, 5.9 %, 71.8 % and 2.3 % distribution, respectively. The largest number of different genotypes were observed within the H1C.2 group with 42 different gene constellations, whereas between 8-13 different genotypes were present in the other three groups. Overall, it appeared that a complete internal cassette of either Eurasian avian-like (EEEEEE, with internal genes in the following order: PB2 (E), PB1 (E), PA (E), NP (E), M (E), NS (E)) or pdm09 origin (PPPPPP) was the most common (43/70 genotypes, 61.4%), whereas when a combination of the internal genes were observed it mainly involved PB1, M and NS gene segments.

For the H1A.3.3.2 group, three HA-NA pairing were observed, and within these three, three and seven genotypes were observed respectively offering different combinations of the six internal genes. The most prevalent genotype within the group across countries was the full H1N1pdm09 (H1A.3.3.2/N1P/PPPPPP) genotype with all eight gene segments of H1N1pdm09 origin constituting 36 % of the strains within the group and 7 % of the total genotyped strains. Another genotype observed across many different European countries was the H1A.3.3.2/N2G.2 with a complete internal gene cassette of pdm09 origin (PPPPPP). Additionally, the H1A.3.3.2/N1EA HA and NA combination were present with three different internal gene constellations, with PPPPPE and PPPPPP being most common and mainly observed in Denmark and Italy. The remaining genotypes were detected only in a few cases and countries.

In the H1B.1 group, seven HA and NA pairings were observed and eight different genotypes. The most prevalent across countries were the H1B.1.2.1/N2G.2 with a complete Eurasian avian internal gene cassette (EEEEEE) observed in Belgium, France, Germany and the Netherlands. However, a relatively high number was also observed of the H1B.1.1.1/N2S with a full internal gene cassette of H1N1pdm09 (PPPPPP) origin but only in the UK. Interestingly, in Northern Ireland a genotype (H1B.1.1/N2LAIV98/PPPPPP) was observed carrying an NA gene derived from the TX98 H3N2 live attenuated swine influenza vaccine issued in the USA from 2017 onwards (Vandoorn et al., 2022), underlining a potential reassortment with these vaccine types potentially used in Northern Ireland, or from USA imported vaccinated swine.

The H1C.2 group includes viruses that have circulated in Europe since the late 1970s, and is by far the most numerous and diverse group with seven different HA clades (1C.2.1 to 1C.2.5) and 42 different genotypes. The results revealed that the virus resembling the original introduction of Eurasian avian-like H1N1 (H1C.2.1/N1EA/EEEEEE) in Europe still circulates in several countries including Austria, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Italy and the Netherlands. A very similar genotype, just carrying an HA gene of a different clade (H1C.2.2) also showed a relatively high prevalence in several different countries including Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands and Switzerland. The same virus with an M gene of H1N1pdm09 origin (H1C.2.2/N1EA/EEEEPE) was also observed in many of the same countries such as Denmark, France, Germany and Italy. Interestingly, a virus with both surface genes of Eurasian avian-like origin, but with all internal genes of H1N1pdm09 origin (H1C.2.2/N1EA/PPPPPP) was also observed, however only in one country (Belgium). The majority of the H1C.2.4 viruses were paired with an N2 surface gene, mainly the N2G.2. Hereof the most identified genotype were the H1C.2.4.1/N2G.1/PPPPPP, H1C.2.4.1/N2G.2/PPPPPP, H1C.2.4.2/N2G.2/EEEEEE, H1C.2.4.3/N2-EU-4/EEEEEE, H1C.2.4.3/N2G.2/PPPPPP and H1C.2.4/N2G.1/EEEEEE. Interestingly, some of these H1C.2.4 genotypes were detected at a high level in a single or few countries, hinting at a country-specific evolution of several lineages within the H1C.2 group.

In general, very few H3N2 viruses were submitted and genotyped (n=17). Of these, only five viruses from Italy were of swine-adapted H3N2 origin (H3.1970.1/N2G.1), and carried a complete internal gene cassette of the H1 Eurasian avian-like origin (EEEEEE). The remaining H3N2 viruses were of more recent human seasonal origin, some carrying internal genes of human seasonal origin (HHHHH), but others representing reassortant events with swine viruses carrying internal genes of both Eurasian avian-like H1N1 origin or pdm09 origin.

swIAV genotypes are a useful tool to better assess swIAV co-evolution and potential border crossing events since strains displaying the same genotype and two closely related HA sequences (which is one of the most variable segments) are more likely to come from a similar origin than strains with different genotypes (although, reassortment events can happen). Within the HA phylogeny, four examples were found of samples displaying the same genotype with similar HA sequences in at least two different countries. One was found within the H1C.2.4.2/N2G.2/EEEEEE genotype with a relatively high genetic distance, compared to other examples, between Denmark and France of ~0.037 which corresponds to over 60 mutations (Figure 3A). This genotype corresponds to the “H1avN2#E” genotype described as the newly predominant swIAV in France from 2020 onwards (Richard et al., 2025). However, internal genes’ phylogenies showed that these strains from Denmark were not grouped and were rather scattered along the phylogenies¹. This points towards a co-circulation in both countries rather than a France to Denmark transmission, which is consistent with the limited live pig imports in Denmark from France since 2020². The H1C.2.4/N2G.2/PPPPPE genotype displayed a minimal genetic distance of ~0.009 on HA between sequences of Denmark and Italy (Figure 3B), which corresponds to approximately 15 mutations. However both genotypes were likely circulating previously in both countries, with detections reported in 2017 in Italy and 2019 in Denmark (genome “AH” Chiapponi et al., 2022; Ryt-Hansen et al., 2025). The H1C.2.4.1/N2G.1/PPPPPP was found in Denmark, Germany and Italy with closely related HAs with a genetic distance of ~0.0135 between Denmark and Italy (~23 mutations) and ~0,006 between Denmark and Germany (~10 mutations). This genotype was the most prevalent in Denmark among H1C/N2G strains from 2019 to 2022 (Ryt-Hansen et al., 2025) and was likely identified in Italy from 2017 onwards (1C.2 “T” genotype (Chiapponi et al., 2022)). The H1B.1.2.1/N2G.2/EEEEEE genotype found in Belgium, Germany, France and the Netherlands displayed closely related HA sequences between France and Belgium with a minimal genetic distance of ~0,0077, which corresponds to ~13 mutations (Figure 3D). The samples from France were collected in 2022 and the samples in Belgium were collected in 2024. These examples overall raise the question of potential *in toto* transmission of swIAVs between countries and could be a result of the large export of weaners from Denmark to for example Germany. However, more systematic phylodynamic analyses using data prior to 2022 are required as well as comparisons between countries of live pig imports for reproduction to confirm these findings.

Conclusion

This report highlights the significant progress made by the ESFLU network and Working Group 2 in monitoring the evolution and diversity of swIAVs across Europe between October 2022 and September 2024. Through the collection and analysis of over 6,700 viral sequences from 877 swIAV strains across 20 European countries, this report provides an unprecedented level of insight into the genetic diversity, geographic distribution and genotype composition of swIAVs currently circulating in European pig populations.

1

<https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/HA:groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2024/NP?c=Genotype%20%28HA/NA/PB2%20PB1%20PA%20NP%20M%20NS%29&s=A/sw/Denmark/06253-1/2023.A/sw/Denmark/07046-3/2023.A/swine/Denmark/04062-3/2024.A/swine/Denmark/04866-3/2024>

2

<https://oec.world/en/profile/bilateral-product/pigs/reporter/dnk?selector1201id=1&selector1205id=2020&selector1655id=marketGrowth&selector1211id=1&multihierarchySelector1456-value=eufra&multihierarchySelector1456-type=Exporter+Country&selector1212id=share>

The data confirm the minimal H3N2 circulation among the swine population in Europe while documenting continuous spill-over events of human seasonal IAV into the swine population and highlights that the swine population can serve as a reservoir for older human seasonal IAVs. A dominance of a limited number of major subtypes, such as H1C/N1EA, H1C/N2G and H1A/N1P was observed alongside substantial diversity at the complete subtype and genotype levels, particularly within the Eurasian avian-like lineage (H1C.2), and more so within the H1C.2.4 clade. This diversity includes the presence of complex reassortants between the Eurasian avian-like and pandemic clades on the internal genes, as well as evidence of reassortment on NA with live attenuated vaccine strains in Northern Ireland. The identification of closely related genotypes in multiple countries suggests possible cross-border transmission events or shared viral origins, reinforcing the need for integrated surveillance and biosecurity strategies at the European level, as well as more integrated phylodynamic analyses. This report points towards the need for i) an updated global swIAV genotype nomenclature compared to the existing one (Henritzi et al., 2020) and ii) classification tools working with this genotype annotation such as BV-BRC (Olson et al., 2023), OctoFlu (Anderson et al., 2022) or Nextclade (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>, (Aksamentov et al., 2021)). This would enhance individual swIAV European laboratories' work comparability with one another, thus contributing to pre-pandemic preparedness. The methods used in this report represent an initial step towards this goal, with the disadvantage of requiring the usage of a command-line tool.

The work of ESFLU WG2, including the integration of data into the Nextstrain platform and the collaboration with OFFLU for global pandemic preparedness, underscores the importance of harmonized, high-resolution surveillance. These efforts not only strengthen our understanding of swIAV dynamics but also provide actionable intelligence for vaccine strain selection and public health readiness. This however shows the difficulty in creating updated influenza A vaccines for the swine population at the scale of Europe considering the swIAV diversity reported here.

Continued coordinated efforts, enhanced sampling coverage, and deeper phylodynamic investigations will be critical in the years ahead to maintain effective early warning systems and mitigate the zoonotic and economic risks posed by swIAVs.

Citation

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Figure 3: Examples of swIAV genotypes co-evolution and potential countries border crossing events in Europe. **A.** Example of H1C.2.4.2/N2G.2/EEEEEE genotype found in France and Denmark with a minimal genetic distance of ~0.037 on HA. **B.** Example of H1C.2.4/N2G.2/PPPPPE genotype found in Czech Republic, Denmark and Italy with a Denmark-Italy minimal genetic distance of ~0.009 on HA on the bottom branch. **C.** Example of the H1C.2.4.1/N2G.1/PPPPPP genotype found in Denmark, Germany and Italy with a Denmark-Italy minimal genetic distance of ~0.0135 on HA. **D.** Example of the H1B.1.2.1/N2G.2/EEEEEE genotype found in Belgium, Germany, France and the Netherlands with a Belgium-France minimal genetic distance of ~0.0077 on HA. Thin branches are genotypes that are filtered out.